

THE VIEWS OF STUDENTS ON PORTFOLIO IMPLEMENTATION IN TURKEYⁱ

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to determine the views of the university students about the implementation process with 10 open ended questions. In this study, the case study of qualitative research designs was used. The study group of the study consisted of 25 female students who attended Bolu Abant İzzet Baysal University Faculty of Education and participated in the "Planning and Evaluation in Teaching" course and in the process of portfolio evaluation. Portfolio training was given to the students by the researcher. The students continued their work by forming peer groups in groups of 2, 3, 4 and 5 for 10 weeks. The answers that the students gave to the 10 open ended questions were organized within specific themes. In the process of portfolio application, students are were asked following questions "what they want to do, what they do, what they learn, where they are successful in the study and what difficulties they take, what points they will take care of when they do this work, which personal skills and professional skills they have gained from this work". The opinions and recommendations of the students regarding the portfolio application have been determined.

Keywords: portfolio, views of students, teaching planning and evaluation

1. Introduction

As an alternative method of evaluation, portfolios are of interest to many teachers who want their students to participate in their own assessment process, and at the same time to develop their creative thinking skills and to find a more comprehensive and meaningful way to assess the knowledge and skills of their students. The ability to improve students' creative thinking makes the portfolio an alternative to classical

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assessment tests (Banta, 2003, p.1). For this reason, there is a great need to use alternative measurement and evaluation approaches that provide a more meaningful and comprehensive way to assess the knowledge and skills of students in education.

Portfolio assessment approach is necessary because it demonstrates the knowledge, skills and capacity by means of collecting the student's work for a period, one year, or throughout the entire university life. Therefore, it requires active participation to the evaluation process of the students by using portfolios and combining the selected activities with appropriate methods and techniques. Students pay more attention to the activities that they plan within their own skills and abilities through portfolio practice. (Banta, 2003, pp. 1-2).

In a portfolio, there may be one or more workpieces containing different phases of the study such as a student's portfolio of reports, mind maps, work papers, test results, letters, stories, novel snippets, poetry and draft of a study, draft papers and finished form, only written documents, not audio and video cassettes, diskettes or models. When evaluating a research paper, both the studies carried out in the process (such as draft papers) and the final product can be included in the evaluation. The student is usually included in the decision-making process in his portfolio. In order to gain different perspectives on the academic development of the students, it is important that teachers place different materials within the individual development files (Kaptan and Korkmaz, 2000, p. 214). Portfolio is a collection that aims to demonstrate the students' achievements in various fields during the process. This collection includes a set of criteria for quality decisions, evidence of students' own reflections, and student sections in the chosen context. (Paulsen and Meyer, 1991, p. 60). For this reason, within the portfolio: The learning objectives that the student wants to reach, the goals or objectives of the studies which the student puts into the portfolio, the reasons why the study is chosen, the criteria to be evaluated according to the studies and the self-evaluation of the students are included (Morgil et al., 2004, p. 109).

The aim of the portfolio is to monitor the development of the student, to allow the student to monitor his / her own development, to document the student's learning in time, to determine what the student has actually learned, to enable the student to self-assess and to facilitate communication with parents, to provide information about the student to the following years, and to provide realistic results about the student's learning. The portfolio gives clues and feedback to the student, teacher, parent and school about how the student learns. They also state that they use the portfolio because they create a better communication tool between their parents and teachers (Lambdin and Walker, 1994, p. 318).

The most general purpose of the portfolio is to demonstrate that the student has achieved the specified learning objectives (Bekiroğlu, 2006, p. 3). Baume (2001) lists the objectives of portfolios: (1) filing portfolios for collecting evidence (2) collects and analyzes learning portfolios (3) in gathering and analyzing the collected evidence, and collects and evaluates the qualifications in the assessment and recruitment portfolios in four groups (cited in Vyortkina, 2003, p. 23). The portfolio provides many opportunities to establish dialogue and maintain communication between teachers and students

(Calfee and Perfumo, 1993, p. 536). The development of a positive approach to students and teachers through the portfolio is the strength of the portfolio (Ryan and Kuhs, 1993, p. 77; Stahle and Mitchell, 1993, p. 539). Perkins and Gelfer (1993), in particular, state that the portfolio improves the behavior of school teachers (cited in Benjamin, 2003, p. 12).

According to Wellensiek, Lembens and Schallies (2001), in portfolio applications, the teacher firstly begins with the right and interesting questions and explains the purpose of applying a portfolio to students. The teacher expresses the importance of the study in terms of evaluation to increase the interest of students. After the subject and time frame of the portfolio work are determined, the teacher asks the students to collect material on the subject. In this way, different perspectives on the subject are seen by the students and the collected materials are evaluated in accordance with the objectives (cited in Morgil et al., 2004, p. 109). With the Portfolio application, it is accepted that the access of students and teachers to the teaching materials is easier and more permanent than reaching them without portfolio (Stahle and Mitchell, 1993, p. 541).

In the application of the portfolio, the teacher ensures that each student is in the hands of wide scale records of his / her progress, including scratching, scribbling, correcting and concluding performance. In the portfolio application, the student makes it possible to follow his / her own development in a teaching process instead of evaluating the student success on an exam paper. Portfolio application shows the time, studies, performance, manuscripts, deficiencies and corrections of the students in the learning process. It allows the student to realize that every part of his work, from manuscript to scribbling and correction is important and related to each other. In this sense, portfolio application shows the developments in the student after many steps in a learning task. Henkin (1993)) found in his study that the portfolio provides a real assessment that contributes to the measurement of students' thinking skills (cited in Benjamin, 2003, p. 11).

Portfolios contain documentation of all achievements; students are responsible for the successful completion of their work. At the same time, teachers are also obliged to create opportunities for students to develop their skills in accordance with their own expectations from education (MLO Model, 1999, p. 77). The student learns to put his / her work into the portfolio file and to take pride in his work and to take more responsibility for the study.

The teacher guides the student in evaluating his / her studies. He/she ensures that the student is more conscious in developing his creativity. The portfolio does not replace the classical measurement-evaluation that seeks to answer the question men which student knows more al. Instead, the portfolio looks for the answer of what a student knows. The fact that the teacher makes interesting questions about the students' portfolio application enables the student to create the right goals and learning steps, to create questions to answer the question of what I learn with the portfolio and how to show it. Thus, the prepared studies start to differentiate. In short, in practice, the teacher can only be an inspiration. The student decides for himself / herself, what, how and why, and takes responsibility for the teacher (Morgil et al., 2004, p. 111). The

teacher should support the students for their own personal orientation, rather than regulating the learning of students. This new task of the teacher focuses on encouraging students instead of judging them, instead of imposing ideas on alternatives. This situation provides flexibility to the learning environment (Tezci and Dikici, 2004).

It is necessary to help students decide what to do, what they need to work and what they have to do in order to improve their own skills in developing their own learning to improve their academic achievement and life skills in using portfolios (Hessler and Kuntz, 2003, p. 31). In this respect, teachers and students have important responsibilities in the process of preparing and monitoring a performance task. The establishment of an effective feedback mechanism is of great importance in the success of these practices and evaluations (Büyüköztürk et al., 2007, p. 112). The view that portfolio evaluation gives the teacher a holistic assessment rather than the classical assessment feature (Calfee and Perfumo, 1993, p. 535; Lambdin and Walker, 1994, p. 317; Viechnicki et al. 1993, p. 376 are reported by researchers. As a means of evaluation, student portfolios have an important place in evaluating students' progress and achievements.

In the early 1970s, the students' skills were evaluated through the portfolio. In the late 1980s, portfolios were used to evaluate the effectiveness of education. In 1999, it was shown that portfolios using Web-based technology attracted the interest of many universities and were used for evaluation purposes. (Banta, 2003, p. 2). The portfolio is related to the activities within the class and the enriched evaluations as a result of natural relations. Portfolio includes collecting and reflecting samples from students' work. Thus, it provides convenient possibilities for both guiding the program and authentic evaluations (Kaptan and Korkmaz, 2000, p. 215). Therefore, portfolios are important assessment tools in which people can easily reach the required gains in daily life and in business life (Miller and Daloz, 1989, p. 30).

There is not common definition of portfolio assessment for the people in the field. Portfolio evaluation definitions made by different researchers at different times. To illustrate, portfolio evaluation is defined as the process of systematically collecting information about the student's development and effort in the process (Hanson and Gilkerson, 1999, p. 81; Nilsen, 1997, p. 11).

Portfolio evaluation is achieved through relations and activities in the classroom by achieving during the teaching process. Therefore, it is not compelling in the classroom as it does not require time to block as in classical tests. It is stated that the students who understand the portfolio culture are responsible for what they need to know and do in the classroom and the cooperation in a portfolio evaluation class is the basis (Wolf, 1989, p. 37). In this system, students have the chance to take their own work again; furthermore, both students and teachers can proudly reflect their individual work. Considering all findings, the importance of assessment in learning is once more evident and the need for change in evaluation strategies is easily understood (Bahçeci, 2006, p. 6).

The portfolio reports that the assessment assists the teacher in monitoring and evaluating the student's performance, helping to reveal the student's strengths and

weaknesses in the document collected in the portfolio, and that the teachers can benefit from the portfolio in displaying the student's success, knowledge and attitude (Adams and Hamm, 1992, p. 104).

The aim of this study is to determine the opinions of students about the application process with 10 open ended questions.

2. Methodology

This study is a qualitative research design; case study. Qualitative research employs different philosophical assumptions; strategies of inquiry; and methods of data collection, analysis and interpretation (Creswell 2009, 173). A qualitative approach emphasizes the qualities of entities, processes and meanings that are not experimentally examined or measured in terms of quantity, amount, intensity or frequency (Denzin and Lincoln 2000, p. 8). Put another way, quality refers to a thing's essence and ambience - the what, how, when and where of it. Qualitative research thus refers to the meanings, concepts, definitions, characteristics, metaphors, symbols and description of things (Berg 2007; Demirci and Gümüő 2017).

The study group consisted of 25 female students who took "Planning and Evaluation in Teaching" course from Bolu Abant İzzet Baysal University, Faculty of Education, Department of Elementary Education, and participated in portfolio evaluation. The students were provided with portfolio training by the researcher. The students continued their studies by forming peer groups in groups of 2, 3, 4, and 5.

The course "Planning and Evaluation in Teaching" was carried out on Wednesday and Friday for 10 weeks in the 4th term of undergraduate Program in Preschool Education. Each week, the working group came together for three-hour classes. In this period, two lesson hours are allocated to the planning department and one lesson hour to the evaluation section. Within this period, two lesson hours are allocated to the planning department and one lesson hour to the evaluation section.

3. Results and Discussion

In this section, students' thoughts were discussed about the portfolio implementation process. In addition, the opinions of the students about the application of the portfolio in the planning and evaluation course were evaluated. There were 10 open-ended questions to determine student views on portfolio practice.

In this study, direct quotations of the students are given. With such an approach, it is aimed to introduce the students with a descriptive approach and to draw up the findings under the themes (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2005: 172). Based on these descriptions, it was ensured that the researcher interpreted the findings and the students made inferences with flash sentences.

Students' answers to 10 open-ended questions to determine their views on the portfolio implementation process were organized under specific themes. In the process

of portfolio application, the results based on the thoughts of students are listed in Table 3.1.

**Table 3.1: Student Opinions on Planning and Evaluation Course
in Portfolio Implementation Process**

Categories / Answers	f
What did I try to do in this course process	
- Desired to be able to reach and present the information	7
- Method of self-assessment	6
- Planning with stories and evaluating the process	5
- Preparing excellent individual development file	4
- Refreshing, developing and reflecting your dreams	3
What did I do	
- The habit of criticizing research presentations	12
- Collecting works in the portfolio file	7
- Summarizing the information that has learned again / homework	6
What did I learn	
- Critiques of commenting and planning	10
- Permanent-fun learning and discovering your own learning style	6
- Developing out of space knowledge and sense of responsibility	5
- Self-confidence, working with a group- cooperation	4
Points that I have been successful with the study/ activities	
-Creating activities with residual materials and being creative	8
- Effective expression-reflection and leadership in the group discussion environment	8
- Developing the abilities of story writing- note taking- writing and speaking	5
- Active attendance and active participation by research	2
- Researching with computer – presentation preparation- portfolio editing	2
The points that I have difficulty in the study /activities	
- Daily planning and time	10
- The tempo of the course and the first two weeks of the course	6
- Limited resources and orientation to libraries in other provinces	5
- Story writing and self-expression	2
- Time-consuming process for preparing portfolio file	2
The points that I will pay attention if I do this study again	
- Adding visuals to the portfolio file	10
- Adding all scrap sheets to the portfolio file	8
- Being planned and using library	8
Individual skills that I think that I gaining from this study	
- Improvement of life and problem solving skills- development of creative thinking	8
- Self-confidence- self-expression- criticizing- using time	6
- Research enjoyment and self-learning method	5
- Sharing-commenting-note taking-summarizing-using computer	4
- Thinking openly-communication with group-empathizing and controlling the excitement	2

Professional skills that I think I have gained from this study	
- Being open to innovations and using the necessary techniques	9
- gaining practically and executing the plan with developing material	6
- Being creative and active with the portfolio implementation	5
- Being patient and acting according to needs	3
- Consciousness of following science and technology	2

My ideas and suggestions about the portfolio implementation	
- Extending the most effective and objective evaluation method	14
- The learning process that contributes to all areas of development	11

In the framework of the first open-ended question in the self-assessment form, students were asked to write what they wanted to do in the portfolio implementation process. 7 students have expressed that they, as researcher, firstly try to study the necessary issues in the timely and precisely to investigate and prepare, most importantly, where and how they can find information, to evaluate what they have learned, to share with friends and to try to move away from the planning-evaluation lesson is trying to move away from the have expressed. 6 students have tried to discover the information by researching the invention and they have tried to see what they can do with this task and 4 students want to have a perfect individual development file. In addition, 5 of the students stated that they wanted to write a story in the best way in the planning and evaluation course, and 3 students 3 students expressed their wishes to reflect their dreams in a small way.

When the answers given by the students are analyzed, it can be said that the students' interest in the course and their knowledge related to the course increased and this was effective in increasing the student's participation in the course.

In the framework of the second open-ended question in the self-evaluation form, students were asked to write what they were doing during the portfolio implementation process. 12 students expressed that they have gained the habit of criticizing by making presentation all the researches they have done. 7 students, various research, expressed that they tried to add visuality and collect their files in the portfolio files by making their files effective and striking with appropriate pictures. 6 students stated that they worked at home and their knowledge is more persistent in the home by summarizing the information they have learned in the classroom. This finding in this research is in line with the finding of Doğan (2005) which is in the process of fourth grade science lesson portfolio implementation students was more careful by doing their homework and that the qualifications of the studies were better and more permanent than their predecessors. Aslanoğlu (2007) stated that in increasing the frequency of doing homework by students has a positive effect on student characteristics.

This situation shows that the students participate actively in the course, discuss the subjects in the course environment, prepare their homework by completing their deficiencies and completing their homework. In another study, it is stated that the time allocated to homework increases students' performance (De Jong et al., 2000, p. 61).

Because homework packages require the student to try to solve the node, he / she says that it is the most important resource about the development of the student and he / she considers these activities as a useful tool about the evaluation method (Gilkerson and Hanson, 2000, p.199). In addition, it can be said that the students' effort to do more research while doing their homework plays an important role in increasing the quality of their homework.

In the framework of the third open-ended question in the self-assessment form, students were asked to write down what they learned during the portfolio implementation process. 10 of the students in the planning and evaluation course stated that they have learned effective teaching-learning methods, the subtleties of doing research, planned-regular work, to interpret and evaluate themselves, the characteristics of the preschool program, the importance of planning, and critiques of planning are important to use not only in education life but also in daily life. In a study by Freiberg and Driscoll (1992), they observed that planning made the process more aimed and increased the efficiency of teaching (cited in Johnson, 2000, p.76). 6 students stated that the classical method was boring, and that more and more fun and permanent learning was realized through portfolio evaluation and that they discovered their own learning style when they were learning the types of learning. These results are in line with the finding of Ersoy (2006) that students see the evaluation based on development file as an objective and performance assessment and should be used in education. 5 students have gone beyond the planning and evaluation course and have contributed to their individual development by developing new knowledge and sense of responsibility. It is seen that the evaluation based on the portfolio contributes to the personal development of preservice teachers in terms of active participation and cooperation in the learning process, motivation for learning, self-confidence, self-assessment, decision-making, problem solving and development of research skills (Pekkanlı, 2003; Dutt-Doner and Personett 1997, p.27; Dutt-Doner and Gilman, 1998, p.160). Four of the students stated that *"Besides my qualification, I realized that my deficiencies were gradually completed, I trusted myself, and I learned to work with the group and collaborating"*. Similar findings are reported by Bahçeci (2006), who investigated the effect of using portfolios on students' cognitive and affective characteristics in anatomy class.

These findings may be an indication that the students give importance to the situation of bringing their research to the class and expressing their self-expression and they have developed important skills to solve problems for their professional life by fusing better with their friends in other departments. Many authors state that there is a rich history in dealing with the complexity of the teaching and learning process in the use of portfolio-based assessment of teacher education and professional development programs (Anderson and DeMulle, 1998, p.26; Barton and Collins, 1993, p.203; Diez, 2001, p. 37; Klenowski, 2001, p.67). As can be seen, it can be said that students' perceptions of the benefits of portfolio application and the benefits in the literature are in parallel.

In the framework of the fourth open-ended question in the self-assessment form, students were asked to write the points / activities they were successful about during the portfolio implementation process. 8 of the students stated that they developed a good personal and professional development in the portfolio file arrangement and they found themselves successful in every point of their work because all the studies are permanent. This result is in line with the findings of Ryan and Kuhs (1993), Rolheiser and Schwartz (2001)'s finding of a visual collection of students and the finding of Ersoy (2006)'s teacher candidates' development files as a source file that they can use in professional field. This situation shows that the students have a good progress in preparing portfolio files, they can use them as a good document in their daily and professional life and they found themselves successful in every point of their studies.

8 students stated that they were very successful in expressing and reflecting the information that is contrary to their ideas with other groups in the appropriate discussion environment in group activities. Groom and Maunonen-Eskelinen (2006) emphasize that in the study of the use of portfolios in the development of reflective practices in teacher education, prospective teachers contribute to the development of skills to evaluate, critique and reflect their own life with this method. Therefore, it can be said that the students have more effective communication skills by exchanging information with the people in large and small groups. 5 students stated that they are successful of, making daily plans, writing stories and writing notes in the process of developing writing and speaking skills, 2 students expressed that come to the course ready for research and active participation in all matters and information provides more permanent, and the other 2 students expressed that they found themselves successful by developing themselves about presentation and making research by computer, internet.

The finding of Öztürk (2004) which is students use other sources than textbooks with this study and there is a significant difference of increase of time of working is parallel with the finding of Unal (1991) that presentation of subjects that students prepared by themselves has positive effect on their success.

In the framework of the fifth open-ended question in the self-evaluation form, students were asked to write the points / activities that they had difficulty in working with during the portfolio implementation process. 10 of the students stated that they want to make more resources in case of more time. 6 of the students stated that they have difficulty with giving lecture because of the tempo of the course, 5 students stated that they are directed to other libraries in other cities because of the limited sources, 2 students stated that it is difficult to prepare portfolio files timely although they did not care much. The opinions of the students that the portfolio based evaluation is a time-consuming process are in parallel with the findings of Birgin (2006), Breault (2004) and Laurence (2003)'s teacher candidates' perception of the portfolio as a time-consuming process.

These difficulties show that students have difficulty with making plan firstly, adapting themselves with changing and developing preschool program, and expressing themselves. They overcome these difficulties by speaking at the discussion platform in

the classroom. This opinion of the students is in line with the opinion in the research (Bartonerun and Collinsdein, 1993, p.205) that portfolio implementation helps expression of students' emotions and thoughts in a more comfortable way. The evaluation of the stories that the students created after each application by their peers and teachers has enabled the student to see himself from two different perspectives. In addition, the fact that the students are aware of the evaluation criteria shows that they are increasing their performance during the story writing process.

In the framework of the sixth open-ended question included in the self-assessment form, students were asked to write the points they would pay attention to if they did this work again. 10 of the students reported positive opinion that they can colorful studies by adding visuality to portfolio files and they want to make everybody see this study in the future. It matches with the finding of Mokhtari et al. (1996) which suggests that portfolio based implementations have positive impact on preservice teachers' positive attitudes and experiences. 8 students stated that they want to be more planned, use library when they research and other 8 students noted that if they were more careful about the layout of portfolio they would not add draft papers. Considering this aspect, it can be thought that almost all of the students who are participated the evaluation process based on portfolio are willing to research and investigate visually, they have a chance to display better performance rather than classical method, hence, they have positive emotions to reflect their skills to everybody as their wish that everybody reads portfolios. In addition, the portfolio supports students' intellectual skills.

In the framework of the seventh open-ended question in the self-assessment form, students were asked to write the personal skills that they thought gained from this study during the process of applying the portfolio. 8 of the students claim that their living and problem solving skills increased, and imagination is developed, 6 students stated that they have the ability of self-expression and make themselves feel better about self-confidence, responsibility and knowledge, also they gain ability of using time efficiently, eye contact, self-evaluation and self-criticizing. In a research about student opinion and importance of portfolio, opinion of a student's *"I'm really lucky when I look at where I am and I feel safer when I look at where I go."* And another student's opinion *"As I think about how much I know about people and their complex problems, I see that I know so little"* are commented by researcher as *"This kind of answer is due to trust"* (Spicuzza, 2003, s.66) and this matches with the finding of this study. 5 students stated that they understood how to learn the enjoyment of research and make a course more permanent, they realized their method of learning as their writing skill is developed and they documented them by recording their information by making portfolio. 4 students stated that they have achieved gains in many areas such as developing their skills of sharing, using computers, making comments, summarizing, taking notes, understanding and comprehending them. Such findings suggest that working behavior can be improved by different learning and evaluation methods. 2 students stated that by creative and broad thinking they gain the abilities of communicate with friends, working with groups, empathy and most importantly beating their enthusiasm with self-confidence. In the

study of Ersoy (2006), evaluating based on development file contributes creativity, thinking, researching, problem solving and using technology. The findings support the findings of this study. Briefly, the portfolio application culture positively affects students' learning as well as their development in all aspects.

All these results indicate that the use of the portfolio puts students in the forefront of the teaching process, encourages students to work together with their friends and connects them with theoretical knowledge and practice by making meaningful connections, emphasizes the importance of shared objectives, and enhances the critical thinking by providing reflection of changing and developing advances in the process (Barton, 1993, p.208) shows a great parallelism with the findings. Active work, practice and creating a discussion environment are positive impacts of this course on student success (Unal, 1991, p.10). In the determination of the evaluation criteria, live classroom discussions between the learners and the learner-teachers provide an important place for the students and the teachers and educational environment for teachers (Mullin, 1998, p.84). The sense of trust that has been developed with the application of portfolio has enabled students to recognize their skills deficiencies and information gaps. They have the power and confidence to see how far they are developing by studying themselves. Moreover, it can be thought that the students need to continue learning and development, revealing different ideas with in-class discussions and contributing to their personal skills by making them gain. Darling (2001), in his research with university students, has reached the conclusion that portfolio based assessment develops thinking skills. In this case, in order to contribute to the personal development of the students, the implementation of the activities for the planning of high-level thinking skills such as research, problem solving, story-building and project can be included.

In the framework of the eighth open-ended question included in the self-assessment form, students were asked to write the professional skills they thought gained from this study during the portfolio implementation process. 9 students stated that they were able to use the necessary methods and techniques by working on open-plan and programmatic approaches. 6 students said that they developed plan and practicality by developing various materials in daily life, 5 students said that the application of portfolio has enabled them to be more creative and active in terms of their professional life, 3 students claimed that they gain abilities like being patient, the importance of student-centered education and professional experience, according to the needs of the ability to act according such as 3 students, to be patient, choosing the product to allow the child to make decisions, and 2 students stated that they are aware of the competencies of teachers by following science and technology and they think that they have developed themselves. These findings are parallel with Ersoy (2006)'s findings that pre-service teachers indicate that the teacher understands the duties and responsibilities of the teacher, the principles of the teaching and the level of the students who will teach them, and the fact that they can see their deficiencies in the vocational field and make plans in areas where they need professional development. It is in parallel with the findings of Bahçeci (2006) and Altay (2003) that the evaluation file-

based assessment reflects the students' own experiences in the professional field, gives them the opportunity to know themselves and starts to see different ways of teaching. Similarly, in the study of Spence and Al-Ansari (2004), teacher candidates stated that they had learned to evaluate themselves.

In this respect, the portfolio application and evaluation study revealed the students' professional identity and the solid foundations of their future development. (Spicuzza, 2003, pg.66). Students had a clear evidence of their ability to create a portfolio file, which allowed them to respect and appreciate the breadth and depth of their educational experience. By developing their assessment and evaluation skills furtherly, students have to be more creative and active in current life, and they have to learn more by using research methods and techniques. In addition, it gains value in the way of making plan-application-evaluation and practicality in daily life.

In the framework of the ninth open-ended question in the self-assessment form, students were asked to write down their ideas and suggestions about the application of the portfolio during the portfolio implementation process. 14 students said that the application of portfolio should be disseminated since it is a study that can be used in every step and it is the most effective objective assessment method. *"I suggest that all courses should be processed and evaluated in line with this system. The study of portfolio can be used in every age and every step"*. This finding of the study coincides with the findings of Tezci and Dikici (2004)'s assessment based on the individual development file, which can be applied successfully in every age group and at each grade level.

In other study, Çelik and Onal (2003) stated that the evaluation of success of students should be done with theoretical and implementation dimensions. Students claimed that preschool students should definitely use a portfolio. For example, in the first year, the portfolio system should be started and at the end of the four-fifth grade, these files should be evaluated separately and delivered to the required authorities. I think the portfolio should be expanded. Different from classical evaluation is the most effective and objective evaluation method. This finding coincides with the finding that Breault (2004)'s teacher candidates found that portfolio-based assessment was more effective, objective and permanent than classical evaluation.

In addition, these findings support the findings of this study that Bolat and Kayhan (2004)'s portfolio-based assessment includes continuity in the development of primary school students, gives importance to observation and personal skills, and is a more suitable, effective system in measuring and evaluating their achievements than in classical examinations.

11 students stated that portfolio application is a very effective method that will help individuals with their development areas and contribute to their personality. They believe that everyone is able to improve their performance by following his / her own development and the individual is competing with his / her own and believes that the process is more important than the product with this evaluation. A student's words on this subject are as follows: *"Portfolio application is a study that must be applied to every individual. One's self-confidence, the ability to see what he can do, and to be useful to him and others around him, as well as to provide behavior, is an evaluation method that renews itself"*

every day and individuals determine the boundaries of their performance. It is a very effective method that will help individuals with their whole development areas and contribute to their personality. With this assessment, everyone can monitor their own development. I saw that my performance improved, the process was more important than the product. I competed with myself. I went after what I could do better, more different. It is important that the student, who has to do this as a priority, develop a plan according to him after thoroughly examining the work calendar. In summary, portfolio implementation was a very effective learning process for me. I found the environment of self-awareness and self-expression. It gave me confidence that I prepared my portfolio file as a book". The results of this study is parallel with Çeğindir (2006)'s finding that 93% of the students are satisfied to participate in the portfolio evaluation process and this has a positive effect on their success.

3.1. Flash Sentences

On the other hand, when the opinions and suggestions of the university students about the application of the portfolio were examined, it was observed that they interacted within the group to resolve the deficiencies. These gains prove students' expressions in flash phrases. The striking sentences related to the portfolio implementation process obtained from the 10th open-ended question related to this subject are given in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Flash Sentences That Express Students' Portfolio Application Process

Student Number	Flash Sentences
1	A single portfolio is enough for me! Thanks...
2	Portfolio implementation process is a process of change.
3	The portfolio also allows the student to monitor their own development.
4	What I do is a guarantee of what I will do.
5	A very special study worth everything!
6	By exploring, exploring, we can learn the whole world.
7	We found by researching we presented by portfolio!
8	You still haven't recognized yourself? Here's an opportunity for you, portfolio!
9	The folder of sharing information.
10	Do it what you want as you want, do it when you want!
11	My portfolio is reflection of the course of planning and evaluation to my life.
12	Portfolio is the process of developing and growing.
13	It's a method of teaching the process of learning.
14	Portfolio is researching, learning, permanence, and mirror of yourself.
15	The most enduring learning is the portfolio through research and self-expression.
16	Plan to use time effectively.
17	Use your portfolio evaluation! Catch the chance of evaluating yourself!
18	Portfolyo is an evaluation which is based on process and performance rather than product.
19	I searched and I learned.
20	My gains.
21	Evaluate the students with the portfolio and follow their progress closely!
22	A process that allows a person to know himself, to discover and to present his work.
23	If you want to see what you can do, prepare a portfolio file.
24	Get your life planned and effective with Portfolio!
25	If you really want to learn, create a portfolio!

As seen in Table 3.2, when the results of the portfolio-based assessment in terms of students' flash sentences for the Planning and Evaluation course in Teaching are analyzed, it is seen that the portfolio evaluation group has positive emotions and thoughts. Based on all these self-assessment comments, it can be said that the application of the portfolio increases the active participation of the students in the Planning and Evaluation course in Teaching. Data from three separate self-assessment forms support each other.

When the answers to the questions of “*What kind of effects does the assessment based on portfolio have on students? Will these change their educational experience perceptions?*” are sought; Buschman (1993); Knight and Gallaro (1994); Research by Paulson and Paulson (1990) reveals the value and superiority of portfolio-based assessment. The common point of view of educators on this subject is concentrated on the students' level of learning in the portfolio based evaluation process. Therefore, students' professional and personal development is based on the portfolio-based evaluation process and product (Akt. Spicuzza, 2003, p.64).

Portfolio develops students' professional skills and they create a source of trust for their professional life in the future. In this study, all the students in the portfolio group gained awareness with the sense of trust by creating their stories as learners. This gave them respect and respect for their educational achievements, and of varying dimensions of experience.

Each student stated that he would start his professional life with a great sense of proficiency, felt safer and was very well prepared for life. While some of the students proposed their life skills such as problem solving, writing, speaking, listening and evaluating skills, some of them expressed their opinions on their development, such as empathy, self-renewal and reflecting their dreams a little. In literature research, the portfolio is referred to as an excellent tool in evaluating personal and professional development, skill development, and educational goals. The portfolio is discussed as an experience of empowerment in self-evaluation, self-motivation, self-esteem and further development (Spicuzza, 2003, p.68).

At the end of the study, students from twenty-five portfolio groups who participated in the experimental process were asked to evaluate the implementation process; the students emphasized that the portfolio based assessment is a more enjoyable application, which increases the motivation, and is a complementary experience and confidence building.

Table 3.2 is seen with the flash sentences that express the portfolio implementation process in which the students take risks and reflect themselves with their efforts in preparing a successful portfolio file. Therefore, these practices and behaviors will not occur unless an appropriate learning environment is established. As a result of this initiative, students have also fulfilled their task of creating portfolio files without any boredom.

It is important to see what these results can be achieved by the efforts made by both academic staff and students for the first time and to create new opportunities when different environments are presented.

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